

Toward Smart Forestry: A Review on Vision-based Perception for Terrain Classification and Obstacle Detection

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Abstract—Ground autonomous systems are increasingly being explored for forestry applications, offering potential to improve safety, efficiency, and scalability in operations such as harvesting, monitoring, and transportation. A fundamental component enabling this autonomy is perception, which allows machines to understand and react to complex environments. This paper presents a comprehensive review of vision-based perception techniques for forestry, with a particular focus on terrain classification and obstacle detection. For terrain classification, we examine four areas: learning-based approaches for terrain understanding; fusion of visual and proprioceptive sensory information for enhanced classification accuracy; terrain property estimation techniques for assessing surface characteristics such as slope and traversability; and vegetation classification methods for distinguishing plant structures that impact navigation decisions. In obstacle detection, we systematically analyze five critical categories: terrain-related obstacles including rocks, roots, and uneven surfaces; vegetation-based obstacles such as fallen trees and dense undergrowth; wild animals that pose dynamic threats to autonomous operations; environmental obstacles including lighting variations, fire/smoke, and weather conditions; and debris and ground-level obstacles such as scattered branches, stumps, and human-made objects. Covering literature from 2019 to 2025, this review highlights the current state-of-the-art, identifies key limitations, and outlines future research directions for deploying perception systems in real-world forestry scenarios.

Index Terms—Terrain classification, obstacle detection, vision-based perception, smart forestry, deep learning, sensor fusion.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the context of smart forestry and autonomous ground mobility, perception forms the cornerstone of vehicle autonomy, enabling machines to interpret and respond to their surroundings. Unlike structured urban environments, forests present highly unstructured and dynamic conditions, characterized by uneven terrain, dense vegetation, fallen debris, and a mix of static and moving obstacles. These elements create unpredictable scenarios that challenge conventional navigation methods and demand far more robust solutions. As a result, the development of advanced perception systems is critical for ensuring that autonomous vehicles can adapt to environmental variability, maintain operational safety, and perform tasks such as path planning, obstacle avoidance, and mission execution with reliability and efficiency.

Among the sensing modalities available, vision-based perception has emerged as particularly promising, offering affordability, rich contextual information, and strong compatibility with modern learning-based frameworks. Camera systems, ranging from monocular and stereo to RGB-D configurations, provide high-resolution data well suited for object detection, semantic segmentation, and scene understanding. However, their deployment in forestry requires overcoming additional challenges such as highly variable lighting, seasonal transformations, frequent occlusions, and dense clutter. Addressing these factors is essential to extend the success of vision-based perception from controlled domains into the demanding realities of autonomous operations in forest environments.

One of the critical perception tasks in forestry is terrain classification, which involves analyzing visual or fused sensor data to differentiate between drivable and non-drivable surfaces. Accurate terrain classification enables autonomous vehicles to adapt their motion to different surface types and anticipate rough or slippery areas, each of which presents distinct mobility challenges. For example, dirt and gravel can reduce traction, mud can cause wheel slip and vehicle bogging, and moss or wet surfaces increase slipperiness, requiring the vehicle to anticipate and compensate for these hazards.

Another essential component is obstacle detection, which ensures operational safety and efficiency. Vision-based systems are able to detect a wide variety of obstacles, such as tree trunks, rocks, logs, branches, wildlife, and other machinery. This task is particularly challenging due to the variability in object appearance, irregular geometries, and the possibility of partial occlusion. Approaches reviewed in this paper include lightweight Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) for real-time obstacle detection, transformer-based architectures for contextual scene understanding, and reinforcement learning frameworks for adaptive avoidance. Additionally, sensor-fusion methods (e.g., RGB-D + IMU, LiDAR + vision) are emphasized as crucial for overcoming visual degradation under challenging forest conditions. Together, these approaches demonstrate the current progress toward building perception systems that are accurate, efficient, and robust enough for real-world forestry deployment.

In this review, a wide spectrum of approaches has been surveyed, ranging from classical machine learning and handcrafted feature extraction to modern deep learning, transformer-based models, and self-supervised learning. Ad-

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ditionally, multi-modal fusion techniques that combine visual, LiDAR, and proprioceptive information are examined for their robustness in dynamic and unstructured environments. These methods are further extended to specialized forestry tasks such as vegetation classification, fire and smoke detection, and wildlife monitoring, which are essential for both navigation and ecosystem safety. By organizing the review around terrain classification, traversability, and obstacle detection, we present an integrated perspective on how perception systems enable automated forestry operations. As forest environments continue to be a promising application domain for automation (e.g., automated harvesting [1], timber transportation [2], forest inventory [3], [4], and fire risk monitoring [5], [6]), the development of robust vision-based perception systems for terrain classification and obstacle detection remains a vital research and engineering focus. These capabilities directly impact the reliability, adaptability, and autonomy of next-generation forestry vehicles and robotic platforms.

II. TERRAIN CLASSIFICATION, TRAVERSABILITY, AND NAVIGABILITY

Terrain classification acts as a critical input that informs both traversability and navigability assessments [7]. By classifying terrain types based on visual, geometric, or proprioceptive data, a vehicle can determine whether specific terrain areas are physically suitable for traversal. For instance, terrain classes such as muddy soil, dense vegetation, gravel, or rocky slopes directly influence traversability by affecting factors like surface friction, roughness, softness, or the risk of mechanical failure.

Once terrain classification has identified these characteristics, traversability analysis uses the classified information to determine whether the vehicle can safely and effectively cross the identified terrain types. Traversability maps or cost functions generated from terrain classification enable autonomous systems to differentiate navigable from non-navigable areas, thus informing safer and more efficient path-planning strategies. By integrating detailed terrain properties, such as softness or slipperiness, into the traversability analysis, autonomous systems can proactively avoid potentially hazardous areas, ensuring operational safety and stability [8].

Navigability builds further upon traversability by incorporating additional layers of complexity, including perception, localization, and dynamic planning capabilities. While traversability assessment provides an initial indication of whether terrain is physically passable, navigability additionally considers if the system can reliably perceive its surroundings, maintain accurate localization, and effectively respond to changing conditions. For example, even if terrain classification indicates that an area is traversable, poor localization due to environmental factors (e.g., dense tree canopies limiting GPS accuracy) or sensor occlusions might reduce navigability, compelling the vehicle to find alternate routes.

Recent studies highlight the importance of deep learning, sensor fusion, and multi-modal data integration as key research directions. However, a variety of methods and application domains continue to be explored, reflecting the diversity and complexity of these environments.

A. Learning-based approaches

Deep learning techniques have been widely applied to forest stand delineation and vegetation classification, which are particularly challenging due to dense canopies and complex boundaries. Sandum et al. [9] employed U-Net architectures trained on multispectral imagery and airborne laser scanning (ALS) data to segment forest areas into multiple classes, non-forest, bare forest land (Stage I), recently regenerated forest (Stage II), young production forest (Stage III), old production forest (Stage IV), and mature forest (Stage V). Their approach re-framed manual stand delineation as an image segmentation task and achieved a moderate pixel-level accuracy of 73%. While this demonstrated the potential of deep learning to assist forestry mapping, it also highlighted its limitations, particularly when dealing with low-quality data or ambiguous labels. To address these challenges, Bello et al. [10] proposed a self-supervised learning framework that used TanDEM-X interferometric SAR data to overcome the scarcity of labelled samples in high-resolution forest mapping. Their method effectively extracted useful features without extensive annotations and significantly improved the detection of fine-scale features, such as narrow roads and forest edges. This approach was especially valuable for expanding forest monitoring in remote or inaccessible regions like the Amazon.

In recent years, researchers have shifted from traditional appearance-based classification towards more robust and actionable terrain understanding techniques that directly support navigation and motion planning. This evolution can be traced through multiple complementary lines of work, each addressing different aspects such as computational efficiency, multi-modal perception, semantic granularity, and real-time performance. Meng et al. [11] proposed TerrainNet, a multi-headed architecture that integrated both semantic and geometric terrain understanding. The model employed self-supervised depth completion from stereo and RGB data to enable fast and adaptive off-road navigation. By focusing on real-time inference and robustness, TerrainNet advanced the field from appearance-based classification toward terrain understanding that was directly actionable for motion planning. While TerrainNet emphasized real-time and multi-headed learning, other works tackled the challenge from the standpoint of model efficiency and suitability for low-power field robots. Wang et al. [12] introduced TSCSPNet, a lightweight terrain segmentation network optimized for efficient and accurate performance on field robots with limited onboard computing resources. Built upon CSPResNet [13], the model integrated Cross-Stage Partial (CSP) connections to reduce computational overhead, Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) for multi-scale feature extraction, and nearest-neighbour interpolation for fast and effective up-sampling. These design choices collectively minimized model complexity while preserving segmentation accuracy. The network was trained and evaluated on the HDU-Terrain dataset [14], a custom-collected dataset from a field robot's viewpoint, comprising over 4,000 frames with pixel-level annotations of varied and unstructured terrain types.

Complementing these approaches aimed at model efficiency, other research explored enhanced semantic granularity for

terrain classification. Gao et al. [15] proposed a contrastive learning-based approach that enabled fine-grained semantic segmentation and terrain mapping for off-road scene understanding. The method used a set of human-annotated anchor patches to learn a discriminative feature representation that captured varying levels of traversability. This representation was used to segment RGB imagery into semantically meaningful terrain classes. The proposed method achieved an anchor matching accuracy of 89.8% in cross-scene validation.

In contrast to deep learning-heavy approaches, some works have hybridized classical methods with neural networks to achieve robustness under constraints. Wang et al. [16] proposed a hybrid method that was evaluated using RGB images representing six types of common terrains. The CNN and the support vector machine (SVM) were both trained and tested on their dataset. The CNN was designed with a simplified architecture to suit the limited computational resources of mobile robots, and was employed for multi-class classification of the terrains. In parallel, the SVM was specifically trained to perform a binary classification focused on distinguishing a particular terrain type of high relevance to the application context.

Building on the theme of navigability-aware learning, Guan et al. [17] proposed GANav, a novel group-wise attention mechanism designed to enhance terrain understanding in off-road and unstructured environments using RGB imagery. GANav introduced a group-wise attention loss that enabled coarse-grained semantic segmentation of terrain based on navigability, effectively guiding the network to focus on semantically meaningful groups at low spatial resolution. This mechanism was agnostic to the choice of backbone architecture, thereby enhancing flexibility and scalability. With improvements in mean Intersection over Union (mIoU) ranging from 2.25% to 39.05% on RUGD and 5.17% to 19.06% on RELLIS-3D, GANav surpassed state-of-the-art techniques, according to empirical assessments on two benchmark off-road scene comprehension datasets. Additionally, the authors implemented GANav on ClearPath Jackal and Husky robots and combined it with a deep reinforcement learning (DRL)-based navigation framework. This approach improved the selection of surfaces with greater navigability by 47%, reduced trajectory roughness by 13.9%, and increased the navigation success rate by 10%, according to real-world field tests.

Beyond RGB imagery, some works utilize alternative sensing modalities like radar and infrared to boost terrain recognition performance under challenging conditions. Hu et al. [18] addressed the limitations of traditional Polarimetric Synthetic Aperture Radar (PolSAR) terrain classification methods, which often suffered from weak feature representation. The paper proposed a hybrid vision-based approach that combines a deep CNN with a Conditional Random Field (CRF) model. Specifically, a pre-trained VGG-16 network was used to extract rich and high-level image features, and these features were then refined through a CRF that used contextual information for improved classification. Pawel et al. [19] addressed terrain recognition for mobile robots using deep neural networks trained on RGB-D data, which included RGB images, depth maps, and infrared images. The authors developed a custom

neural network model specifically designed to use the multi-modal vision data for classifying terrain types (e.g. Sand, Rocks, Gravel, Grass, etc.). Their suggested model was divided into two stages. For effective gradient propagation, the first phase of the network consisted of two convolutional layers, each followed by a ReLU activation. To reduce the risk of overfitting, a pooling operation was applied at the end of this phase, followed by a 25% dropout. The second phase mirrored the first, with identical layers and configuration. The output of this stage was then passed to the fully connected layers responsible for classification. The ReLU layer in the fully connected stage received input from 512 neurons, after which a 50% dropout was applied to further improve generalization. Finally, the output layer consisted of nine neurons, each representing a terrain class in one-hot encoding, with a Softmax activation added to provide probabilistic outputs. Experimental results demonstrated that their proposed model achieved 98.99% test accuracy.

A number of approaches also address real-time performance under constrained settings or sensor failure, which is a practical challenge in the field. Al Jarrah [20] proposed a two-stage, vision-based method for real-time terrain detection in unstructured environments, targeting autonomous ground robots with limited computational resources. The first key contribution was a road-type classification framework that distinguished between normal and curved roads using a feature-based clustering model. This classification step simplified the downstream segmentation problem by tailoring the method to the specific road geometry. For normal road terrains, the paper introduced a vanishing point (VP) estimator that combines Gabor filter banks and convolutional neural networks (ConvNets), treating the VP estimation as a regression task. This approach improved both accuracy and computational efficiency compared to existing methods. Once the VP was estimated, it was used to define a sample region for segmentation. A multivariate Gaussian model was then constructed over this region, and segmentation was performed using trapezoidal fuzzy membership functions, which computed pixel-wise thresholds based on orientation data. This method enhanced robustness to noise and lighting variability. For curved road terrains, where traditional VP-based approaches were less reliable, the authors adapted the Fuzzy C-Means (FCM) algorithm into a fast and self-supervised segmentation method. It incorporated morphological reconstruction and membership filtering to improve pre-segmentation quality, yielding better results with shorter runtimes. The proposed system was evaluated on two datasets and deployed on a rover bogie robot. Results showed reliable real-time performance across various terrain types, with the VP estimator and fuzzy segmentation methods achieving a high accuracy of 96.43% under diverse environmental conditions (including different times of day, both indoor and outdoor scenes, varied road shapes (normal and curved), and a range of surface types such as soil, asphalt, pavement, and brick.) without the need for parameter tuning.

Fusic et al. [21] introduced a deep learning-based terrain classification method for autonomous guided vehicles, specifically designed to operate under sensor failure conditions. The authors created and used a custom vision-based dataset

Fig. 1: GANav Framework presented in [17].

(1,400 images) to train and validate semantic segmentation models for identifying obstacles and navigable paths in logistic environments. The core technical contribution was the comparison of two segmentation architectures: U-Net and Mask R-CNN. Results showed that Mask R-CNN significantly outperforms U-Net, achieving 93% accuracy versus U-Net’s 70%. This 23% margin demonstrated that Mask R-CNN was more robust for scene understanding in sensor-compromised scenarios, making it a promising option for improving the reliability of autonomous systems in industrial logistics.

In scenarios where training data is scarce or computational resources are limited, transfer learning has emerged as a practical solution. Krishna Kumar et al. [22] investigated the use of transfer learning with pre-trained ConvNets (ResNet50, VGG16, and InceptionV3) for terrain classification from images. The main contribution was the comparative evaluation of these models on terrain recognition tasks, focusing on managing the complexity of large datasets and high-dimensional features through transfer learning. The results highlighted that all three models performed well, confirming that leveraging pre-trained networks was an effective approach to reduce training complexity while maintaining strong classification accuracy in terrain recognition. This work provided practical insights into model selection for terrain classification problems where data or computational resources might be limited.

Transformer-based architectures are gaining increasing attention in terrain perception tasks. A notable example is StrideNET, introduced by Shelare et al. [23], which featured a dual-branch architecture. One branch used Swin Transformers to capture both global and local contextual features, while the other incorporated statistical texture analysis to infer terrain properties such as roughness and slipperiness. By explicitly modeling surface characteristics, StrideNET demonstrated strong applicability in real-world scenarios involving uneven and dynamic terrains. The model outperformed both traditional CNN-based approaches and earlier transformer-based benchmarks, highlighting the potential of hybrid architectures

in complex perception tasks. Moreover, Hui Chen et al. [24] contributed to terrain classification for walking robots and exoskeletons by introducing a vision-based method that fused RGB and depth data using early and late fusion strategies. The core technical contribution was the use of a Vision Transformer (ViT) to process fused RGB-D inputs, enabling real-time terrain classification across five common walking scenarios (stairs, ramps, and level ground). The authors compared four models: unimodal RGB, unimodal depth, Pre-Fusion (early fusion), and Post-Fusion (late fusion). The Post-Fusion model achieved the highest accuracy (97.64%) and recall (98.07%), slightly outperforming the Pre-Fusion model, while both fusion models significantly outperformed unimodal approaches. However, the Post-Fusion model operated at a lower processing frequency (145 Hz), compared to faster but less accurate models like the unimodal depth model (311 Hz). The study also included attention weight visualizations from the ViT model, offering interpretability into how different features (e.g., texture and depth) influence classification. Overall, the findings showed that while Post-Fusion offered the best accuracy for critical applications, Pre-Fusion provided a strong balance of accuracy and speed, making it more flexible for real-world deployment.

B. Fusion of visual and proprioceptive features

Visual features are extracted from external cameras and are used to classify terrain based on appearance and structure. These features may include colour, texture, edge patterns, surface geometry, etc. For instance, grassy areas often appear green and textured, while paved roads are typically smooth and uniform. Such features enable the system to recognize terrain types from a distance, supporting predictive planning. However, visual perception can be sensitive to lighting changes, shadows, dust, and occlusion, reducing its reliability in some off-road environments. In contrast, proprioceptive features, which are derived from internal sensor measurements, classify terrain based on the vehicle’s physical interaction with the

environment. These include wheel slip, suspension dynamics, IMU data, motor torque feedback, etc. Unlike vision-based approaches, proprioceptive terrain classification is robust to environmental visibility and lighting conditions, making it particularly effective in unstructured and low-visibility settings. By analyzing the vehicle’s real-time response to varying terrain, these features support accurate terrain recognition and adaptive control.

Combining visual and proprioceptive features offers the most robust approach to terrain classification. Visual features provide long-range, appearance-based information, enabling early predictions, while proprioceptive features offer reliable, real-time feedback based on the vehicle’s physical interaction with the terrain. By fusing both types, the system can provide more accurate and resilient terrain recognition in diverse and challenging environments.

Building on this understanding, researchers have explored multiple fusion strategies and architectures that leverage the complementary nature of visual and proprioceptive data. These studies vary in fusion level (early, feature, or decision), adaptability to lighting and terrain conditions, and target platforms (wheeled, legged, or tracked robots). For instance, Chen et al. [25] proposed a decision-level sensor fusion strategy combining proprioceptive and visual inputs. Two independent CNNs were trained separately: ProprioceptionNet processes inertial and mechanical signals, while VisionNet classified terrain appearance from RGB imagery. Rather than fusing features at the input or intermediate levels, the authors applied a late-fusion scheme, combining softmax outputs from both networks. This allowed each modality to retain its specialized processing while avoiding the complexity and computational burden of joint training. Both networks remained frozen during fusion, enhancing efficiency and modularity. Experimental results across four lighting conditions showed that the decision-level fusion approach achieved superior generalization, with an average accuracy of 96.40%, outperforming both unimodal baselines and feature-level fusion models. Moreover, the framework demonstrated strong robustness to lighting variations and terrain textures, while simplifying system integration by removing the need for time synchronization or feature alignment across modalities. Extending the concept of adaptive fusion, Hsiao et al. [26] proposed a novel multimodal framework integrating proprioceptive inputs, such as wheel speeds and IMU measurements, with visual appearance features, including texture descriptors, color histograms, and grayscale textures. To tackle the challenge of low-light environments, the authors introduced a fuzzy logic-based tuning mechanism that adaptively adjusted the weighting of sensor inputs according to ambient illumination conditions. This fuzzy tuner enabled the system to rely more heavily on reliable data streams (e.g., IMU readings) when visual features became less dependable due to insufficient lighting. The fuzzy-tuning mechanism improved classification performance under low-light scenarios, while a reduced-order model utilizing a one-dimensional CNN significantly reduced the computational complexity associated with feature extraction and classification tasks. This lower complexity allowed the framework to operate effectively on resource-constrained com-

putational platforms without compromising accuracy. Notably, this method achieved classification accuracy as high as 99.7% using Near-Infrared (NIR) images. Compared to traditional unimodal approaches, such as those relying exclusively on visual inputs (e.g., texture or color-based classification methods using SVM or standard CNNs) or solely on proprioceptive sensors (e.g., odometry-based navigation), this multimodal fusion approach demonstrated superior adaptability and reliability. The proposed method clearly illustrated the benefits of fusing multiple sensor modalities, leading to improved and consistent performance across diverse environmental conditions.

Moving toward more complex environments, particularly for legged locomotion, Sun et al. [27] proposed a comprehensive vision-based perception framework for legged robots operating in challenging outdoor settings such as forests and hilly terrains. Their approach integrated a rich array of sensors, including binocular cameras, IMU, force sensors, and infrared sensors, to capture robust and multimodal environmental information. The binocular cameras generated depth maps that detailed terrain geometry and ground features, while the IMU and force sensors provided accurate pose estimation and real-time feedback on ground interactions. Infrared sensors enhanced perception under variable lighting conditions. To construct a resilient environmental representation, the system fused sensory data collected under diverse motion and illumination scenarios. This fusion pipeline fed into a deep learning architecture that combined unsupervised and supervised modules. A sparse autoencoder performed multi-channel feature extraction to generate informative terrain models, and a supervised CNN mapped foot force measurements to terrain types, enabling material classification. Furthermore, semantic segmentation was achieved using a dynamic CNN to identify traversable areas within dense vegetation, significantly improving situational awareness. These integrated capabilities, alongside real-time pose estimation and spatiotemporal modeling, enabled the robot to construct a reliable topological map of its surroundings, thereby enhancing its decision-making and mobility in unstructured natural environments. Additionally, Wisth et al. [28] introduced VILENS, a significant advancement in state estimation for legged robots through the tight integration of visual, inertial, LiDAR, and leg kinematic data within a unified factor graph framework. Unlike loosely coupled systems, where sensor data were processed independently and fused at a high level, VILENS performed joint optimization across all modalities simultaneously. This design enhanced robustness by leveraging the complementary strengths and offsetting the failure modes of each sensor:

- Leg odometry provided continuous velocity estimation but was vulnerable to drift due to slippage or soft terrain.
- Visual odometry offered rich spatial detail but struggled in low-light or textureless scenes.
- LiDAR supplied geometric constraints at lower frequencies and might falter in sparse or repetitive environments.
- IMUs contributed high-rate motion priors but accumulated drift without correction.

By fusing these heterogeneous inputs into a single optimization problem, which allowed the system to maintain accurate,

drift-resilient localization across diverse and challenging terrains, as validated through extensive field trials on ANYmal quadrupeds.

Closing the perception-planning loop, Ren et al. [29] proposed TOP-Nav, a novel legged robot navigation framework that tightly integrated terrain estimation, obstacle avoidance, and closed-loop proprioceptive feedback to enable robust performance in off-road environments. Unlike prior methods that primarily focused on obstacle avoidance, TOP-Nav holistically fused multi-modal sensory data: vision and proprioception at both the path planning and motion planning levels. At the task planning level, the framework incorporated a terrain-aware waypoint selector that optimized traversability while ensuring obstacle avoidance. At the motion level, a locomotion controller executed navigation commands, while a proprioception advisor evaluated motion execution and fed corrective information back to the path planner. This closed-loop architecture enabled the system to adaptively refine visual terrain and obstacle estimates in real time, thereby overcoming the limitations imposed by visual degradation or prior data biases. In real-world experiments, TOP-Nav was evaluated on terrains such as gravel (unseen during training) and slippery tarpaulin. In the Unknown Gravel scenario, TOP-Nav achieved a 7% increase in Useful Travelled distance (UT) compared to GANav, which possessed complete prior terrain knowledge but lacked online correction. In the Slippery Tarpaulin scenario, TOP-Nav significantly improved the navigation success rate by avoiding instability-prone surfaces, outperforming baselines such as Obstacle-Only and Sterling. Despite these improvements, two key limitations are acknowledged: reduced visual odometry robustness under variable lighting conditions and occasional instability in waypoint selection due to costmap-based local planning, which could be mitigated by employing a diffusion-based planner in future work.

Other works highlight diverse fusion strategies and classifiers. Hui et al. [30] proposed a terrain classification method for tracked robots by fusing vibration and image data at the feature level and applying a weighted K-nearest neighbour (WKNN) algorithm for classification. The core contribution lies in extracting 20 time-domain and 8 frequency-domain features from vibration signals, followed by dimensionality reduction using PCA to retain principal components explaining 99% of the variance. In parallel, image texture features are extracted using the gray-level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM). These features are then fused to form a combined representation of the terrain. To improve classification performance, the authors modify the standard KNN algorithm by introducing a distance-based weighting scheme, forming the WKNN classifier. Experimental results show that this combined feature representation, when classified using WKNN, significantly outperforms traditional KNN approaches. At a speed of 0.3 m/s, accuracy increases from 57.14% (KNN with raw data) to 97.14% (WKNN with fused features). At 0.7 m/s, accuracy improves from 60.00% to 91.43%. These results demonstrate that the fusion of PCA-processed vibration features with image texture features, combined with the WKNN classifier, leads to a more accurate and robust terrain recognition system for tracked robots. Similarly, Guan et al. [31] introduced VINet,

a novel terrain classification network that fuses visual and inertial data to improve robotic navigation over various terrains. The key innovation lies in a fusion scheme that aligns latent embeddings from image and inertial sequences channel-wise, along with an IMU denoising strategy to handle noisy inertial measurements, which together enhance classification accuracy. VINet achieves 98.37% accuracy under supervised settings on known terrains and improves accuracy by 8.51% on unknown terrains compared to previous methods. Beyond classification, the authors propose an adaptive scheduling control framework that leverages VINet’s predictions with a novel navigation-based labeling scheme. When deployed on a tracked robot, this framework improves navigation performance, reducing trajectory following error by 10.3% RMSE relative to a baseline single-terrain controller. The paper highlighted the benefit of using navigation-oriented labels instead of traditional semantic ones, enabling safer and more stable navigation on unknown terrains. While the system shows promise, the authors note limitations such as limited testing on multiple unknown terrains in a single run, and suggest future work integrating traversability and obstacle avoidance.

Differently, proprioceptive signals were used to supervise visual learning in real time in the Wild Visual Navigation (WVN) system proposed by Frey et al. [32]. This online, self-supervised framework enabled a quadruped robot to autonomously estimate traversability in unstructured natural environments using only onboard sensors and a brief human demonstration. Rather than relying on pre-collected datasets or extensive offline training, WVN dynamically labeled terrain during operation by monitoring the robot’s own proprioceptive feedback and control signals. Specifically, proprioceptive data (such as joint angles, contact forces, and motion stability) served as a ground-truth indicator of whether the terrain was traversable. Stable and successful steps were labeled as safe, while slippage or instability indicated non-traversable terrain. These self-generated labels supervised the online training of a lightweight neural network built on top of high-dimensional visual features extracted from a pre-trained Vision Transformer (ViT). This enabled the system to adapt to local terrain appearance in real time, even in visually ambiguous or novel environments. To further enhance robustness, WVN incorporated anomaly detection to handle sparse or uncertain supervision, improving performance in ambiguous regions. Integrated with local planning and mapping systems, the robot successfully completed 1.4 km of autonomous navigation with under five minutes of online training. This work demonstrated the potential of proprioception-guided, vision-based terrain learning to support agile, adaptive autonomy in complex natural environments.

Supervised learning still holds relevance for certain domains. Cui et al. [33] introduced a supervised learning approach that modeled the relationship between low-level visual features of terrain images, specifically color and texture and terrain traversability, which was quantified using relative vibration data from an IMU sensor. The key idea was to use these visual features to predict how difficult a given terrain would be for a field robot to traverse. The core technical contribution was the use of SVM regression to learn a mapping from visual

Fig. 2: VINet Framework introduced by Guan et al. [31].

features to a continuous traversability score. To improve generalization and avoid overfitting, the model was trained using k-fold cross-validation, and the optimal hyperparameters were selected through a grid search, minimizing the average mean squared error. Beyond prediction, the paper introduced a post-processing step to convert the raw traversability predictions into smoothed values over spatial sub-regions. These smoothed traversability estimates were then used for path planning, where the robot selected the optimal path by minimizing the cumulative traversability cost across sub-regions. The method was validated through three experiments, showing that the learned model can effectively predict terrain difficulty from vision and contribute to smoother and safer path planning in real-world field environments. Akhil et al. [34] presented a supervised terrain classification (e.g., Grass, Gravel, Fine sand) approach for autonomous ground vehicles (AGVs) operating in off-road environments, using a sensor fusion strategy that combines visual data from a camera with vibration data from an inertial measurement unit (IMU). The key contribution lies in constructing fused feature vectors from synchronized camera images and IMU-derived acceleration statistics, and using these as input to an SVM classifier. The method captures an image of the terrain and then records IMU data as the vehicle traverses the corresponding region. From the IMU, linear acceleration vectors perpendicular to the terrain surface are extracted, and statistical features are computed to represent terrain-induced vibration patterns. These are manually aligned with the image data to form the training set. While individual modalities (camera and IMU) yielded classification accuracies of 87% and 78%, respectively, their fusion improved overall accuracy to 90% on unseen field data. The fused approach enhanced classification performance specifically for grass and gravel terrains, though performance on fine sand decreased slightly, highlighting the benefits and limitations of feature-level fusion. The results confirm that integrating complementary sensor modalities can lead to more robust terrain classification in varied outdoor conditions.

Reinforcement learning-based methods are gaining increasing attention in terrain perception tasks. For instance, Zhou et al. [35] proposed an end-to-end reinforcement learning method for local navigation that fuses multi-modal data. Specifically, IMU data (intrinsic), LiDAR point clouds, and front-view images (extrinsic). Each data type is processed by a dedicated feature extraction network, and the overall system is trained using a modal separation learning approach. This structure allows the network to learn more specialized and complementary features from each sensor type. Experimentally, the method is benchmarked against mono and bi-modal baselines (pose-only, pose+LiDAR, and pose+LiDAR+segmentation). Results show that the proposed tri-modal system outperforms these baselines in handling complex off-road scenarios. It successfully navigates around terrain challenges like steep slopes and pits, and adapts to dynamic conditions, including vegetation and water disturbances. Notably, by adjusting segmentation categories, it also generalizes to obstacles like mud and soft soil, demonstrating both robustness and adaptability in unstructured environments.

Skultety [36] compares a deep-learning approach (Convolutional CNN & ResNet model) for terrain characterization (such as concrete, sand and gravel) against a traditional analytical method [37] that employed a technique known as Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC), both implemented on a wheeled robot equipped with stereo depth, IMU, and GPS sensors. The deep-learning solution was developed alongside the robot's navigation and data processing systems and tested in a real forest environment. The key contribution lies in directly evaluating these two approaches under real-world conditions by measuring metrics like energy consumption and terrain roughness during navigation. The results show that while both methods can support basic navigation, the deep-learning approach requires a large, high-resolution dataset to reach its full potential. The study also identifies the need for improved navigation systems with better global perception to handle complex environments more reliably.

Meanwhile, other researchers explored more specialized or application-driven solutions. Zhao et al. [38] introduced Super Odometry, a multi-sensor fusion framework that emphasized IMU-centric processing for robust and accurate state estimation in perceptually degraded environments. Unlike traditional tightly or loosely coupled sensor fusion methods, Super Odometry combined elements of both approaches to recover motion in a coarse-to-fine manner, integrating data from IMU, LiDAR, and cameras. The system was organized into three primary components: IMU odometry, visual-inertial odometry, and laser-inertial odometry. The IMU odometry provided motion prediction, while the visual and laser branches both used this prediction and, in turn, supplied priors to correct IMU bias. This mutual reinforcement improved robustness, ensuring reliable performance even under sensor degradation or partial failure. A key technical contribution was the use of a dynamic octree for 3D point organization during LiDAR scan matching. This structure reduced runtime to 10% of that required by a traditional KD-tree, making the system more viable for real-time applications. Super Odometry was deployed on both drones and ground robots in various real-world environments, including low-light, dust-heavy, and feature-sparse areas. The system was extensively tested as part of Team Explorer’s entries in the DARPA Subterranean Challenge, contributing to top placements in the Tunnel and Urban circuits, and demonstrating strong performance even under aggressive motion and poor sensing conditions. Elnoor et al. [39] introduced Adaptive Multi-modal Coupling (AMCO), a navigation framework for quadruped robots that adaptively combined vision-based semantic segmentation with proprioception-based sensing to generate a coupled traversability cost map. The key innovation lay in three distinct cost maps: general knowledge (vision), traversability history (proprioception and past experience), and current proprioception, which were weighted based on an image reliability estimation accounting for brightness and motion blur. This adaptive fusion allowed the robot to rely more on proprioception when visual data quality degraded. AMCO used this coupled cost map to guide gait and velocity selection via a novel planner optimized for stability and success in challenging outdoor terrains. The method demonstrated significant improvements in real-world tests: it reduced robot vibration by 10.8% to 34.9% across multiple scenarios and achieved up to a 50% higher success rate compared to several state-of-the-art navigation methods. Experiments highlighted that AMCO proactively switched gaits in anticipation of difficult terrain (e.g., granular sand, vegetation, mud) and avoided unstable regions using recent proprioceptive history. The approach outperformed others, especially in degraded visual conditions, where adaptive weighting prioritized proprioceptive inputs to maintain reliable navigation. The study acknowledged limitations associated with the system’s reliance on proprioceptive sensing in low-light conditions. As a potential avenue for future research, the authors suggested incorporating additional sensing modalities, such as thermal and hyperspectral imaging, as well as exploring the integration of vision-language models, to enhance environmental understanding and improve traversability prediction. Wang et al. [40] presented a terrain preview detection and classification system for emergency res-

cue vehicles that combines deep learning with tightly coupled multi-sensor fusion. The core technical contributions lie in three integrated components: (1) Terrain Classification Using Vision with Transfer Learning: The system uses a ResNet50-based architecture combined with transfer learning to classify terrain types in real time. This setup boosts classification performance while minimizing training time and data requirements. It achieved 98% accuracy on the training dataset and 83% on the test dataset. (2) High-Precision Terrain Mapping via LiDAR-IMU Fusion: A tightly coupled fusion framework integrates LiDAR and IMU data to produce a 3D terrain preview. This approach addresses the typical accumulation errors seen in loosely coupled sensor fusion methods. The resulting terrain mapping achieves an accuracy of approximately 4–5 cm, even in large or complex environments. (3) Decision-Level Fusion for Elevation Extraction: By aligning the classified terrain types (from the vision system) with LiDAR-derived geometry in space and time, the system generates accurate terrain elevation maps. This decision-level fusion improves robustness, especially under challenging conditions like rapid vehicle rotation. Together, these contributions form a real-time, deployable system capable of improving ride comfort and safety through accurate elevation preview and terrain classification. Experimental results show that the proposed method performs better than comparable systems, especially in handling high-dynamic motion scenarios. Huang et al. [41] is the introduction of the MOTC dataset, a multimodal terrain classification dataset tailored for extraterrestrial environments. It was collected using a rover equipped with visual cameras and an IMU. The dataset contains nearly 25,000 annotated samples, categorized into three surface material types and three scene geometries, enabling fine-grained terrain understanding. On top of this dataset, the authors propose a baseline terrain classification model that fuses visual and inertial data. Their results show that combining these two modalities leads to better classification accuracy compared to using either one alone.

By using acoustic information alongside visual input, Zürn et al. [42] proposed a self-supervised terrain classification framework that eliminated the need for manual labeling in robotic perception tasks. An unsupervised audio-based classifier, trained on terrain-induced vehicle interaction sounds, was used to supervise a visual classifier, enabling automatic training label generation for visual terrain segmentation. The inherent robustness of audio features to lighting, weather, and seasonal variations made them ideal for this cross-modal self-supervision strategy. A novel cross-modal triplet mining heuristic was introduced, where visual similarity (extracted via a pre-trained ImageNet model) guided the construction of audio triplets without requiring ground-truth labels. This approach correctly formed 81.35% of audio triplets, significantly improving clustering performance. To learn effective acoustic embeddings, a Siamese Encoder with Reconstruction Loss (SE-R) was designed, combining triplet loss with spectral reconstruction to balance discriminability and noise resilience. The audio-generated clusters were then projected onto image frames using robot trajectory data, producing pseudo-labels for training semantic segmentation networks.

This process achieved 56.53% mIoU. Critically, the system demonstrated lifelong learning through domain adaptation, generalizing to new environments with 94.8% accurate audio relabeling and visual model fine-tuning, all without manual annotations. The full system was validated on the Freiburg Terrains dataset, consisting of four hours of synchronized audio-visual recordings across five terrain types, and achieved state-of-the-art performance in unsupervised clustering (94.8% accuracy, 0.839 NMI) with noise tolerance down to 10 dB SNR, underscoring its suitability for terrain-aware navigation in challenging field environments.

Collectively, these studies illustrate the evolution of terrain perception systems from modular, decision-level fusions to tightly coupled, real-time pipelines optimized for diverse environments and platforms. Whether through late-fusion classifiers, adaptive weighting, or lifelong learning systems, the fusion of visual and proprioceptive modalities remains central to improving terrain understanding and navigation robustness in autonomous ground and legged robots.

C. Terrain property estimation

While many of the studies discussed above focus on terrain classification, others have explored the prediction of physical terrain properties, which is crucial for maintaining robot stability and control. For example, Dong et al. [43] proposed a two-stage framework that predicts terrain stiffness and friction using pixel-level semantic segmentation. Their decision-making module maps image features to physical characteristics, offering a more interpretable approach to terrain assessment. This emphasis on inferring physical properties complements visual classification models by strengthening the connection between perception and control, ultimately enabling more informed and adaptive navigation in complex environments. Another work by Garen et al. [44] proposed an innovative traversability analysis framework that enhances safe navigation over unknown and non-rigid terrains by integrating active terrain probing into a vision-based perception pipeline. Drawing inspiration from human exploratory behavior in uncertain environments, the authors highlight the limitations of relying solely on visual and geometric cues when navigating unpredictable terrains like soft soil, dense vegetation, or water puddles, which may appear passable but pose significant risks to mobile robots. The core innovation lies in the fusion of geometric, semantic, and physical interaction data to construct a multidimensional traversability grid map. The system assesses terrain geometry (e.g., slope, roughness) and semantic features (e.g., vegetation or water regions) using an RGB-D camera. It then identifies regions of uncertainty for targeted probing, which are physically evaluated using a force sensor mounted on the robot to measure terrain collapsibility, defined as the likelihood of structural failure under load. This collapsibility metric is combined with other terrain descriptors to generate both global and local traversability maps, which are subsequently used for robust and informed path planning.

Terrain-aware path planning for autonomous vehicles has seen significant advances through various frameworks that integrate environmental understanding with dynamic decision-

making. Rather than treating traversability as a binary classification problem, recent approaches have emphasized modeling uncertainty, generalization, and context-awareness especially for unstructured, off-road environments. For example, Wang et al. [45] proposed a traversability-aware framework for autonomous wheeled vehicles' path planning on rigid terrains. The framework integrated terrain features and vehicle dynamics to enhance cost modeling and planning accuracy. As shown in Figure 3, the proposed framework included three main components: traversability boundary analysis to filter out impassable regions, cost mapping using segmented linear regression to evaluate how terrain affects performance, and TV-Hybrid A*, a path planner that incorporated a neural network-based cost function for terrain-aware decision-making. Specifically, the traversability boundary analysis approach used theoretical and empirical models to define traversability limits based on geometric (slope, height), physical (friction, roughness), and obstacle-related constraints. This stage produced a binary traversability map, effectively filtering out clearly non-traversable regions to reduce computational overhead. Simulation results showed that TV-Hybrid A* outperforms traditional A* and Hybrid A* in path length, time, and energy efficiency. However, the approach was computationally intensive and currently limited to rigid terrains, reducing its applicability in more dynamic natural environments. Addressing the rigidity limitation, Parker et al. [46] introduced a Bayesian inference framework for real-time terrain property estimation and semantic elevation mapping to enable risk-aware navigation in unstructured environments. Unlike traditional binary traversability classification, their approach probabilistically infers terrain characteristics from RGB-D visual data. The key contribution is a recursive semantic mapping system that integrates a Bayesian estimation model with RGB-D imagery to estimate: (1) the surface elevation profile of the terrain, and (2) probability distributions of critical physical properties such as friction. This probabilistic representation supports uncertainty-aware path planning, enhancing safety and adaptability in challenging off-road conditions.

While Parker's approach estimates terrain properties using a probabilistic model, Fu et al. [47] tackled the challenge of autonomous off-road navigation in unstructured terrains, where traditional physics-based models struggle with non-linear terrain-vehicle interactions and data-driven methods often failed to generalize across different environments and vehicle types. To address this, they introduced AnyNav, a neuro-symbolic framework that integrated deep learning with symbolic physical reasoning for friction estimation and path planning. AnyNav featured a two-layered approach: (1) a neural network estimated terrain friction from visual inputs, which was then passed to a symbolic physics model to reason about traversability and motion feasibility; and (2) a physics-informed planner generated dynamically consistent, friction-aware trajectories and speed profiles. This approach was extensively validated in both simulation and real-world off-road environments using multiple four-wheeled vehicle platforms. Results demonstrate that AnyNav delivered robust navigation across varied terrain types, outperforming baseline methods by generating physically consistent paths that adapted to terrain-

Fig. 3: The proposed framework of traversability analysis and path planning methods for autonomous wheeled vehicles on rigid terrains [45].

specific friction conditions. This significantly reduced risks, such as slippage, instability, and energy inefficiency. Compared to Parker et al. [46], who focused on estimation under uncertainty, Fu et al. [47] took it a step further by integrating that estimation into a complete planning and control loop, validating it across multiple vehicles and environments.

The question of data scarcity, particularly in unfamiliar or high-risk environments, was tackled by Inotsume et al. [48] who proposed an adaptive terrain traversability prediction framework to improve off-road vehicle mobility in unfamiliar environments, particularly where little or no prior data existed for high-risk terrain. Accurate prediction of slippage and energy consumption on steep or unconsolidated surfaces is essential for safe, efficient navigation. However, most learning-based methods require large and terrain-specific datasets, limiting their usefulness in data-scarce situations. To overcome this, the authors developed a multi-source transfer learning approach using Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), which used prior data from various terrains and combined it with limited observations from low-risk areas of the target environment. This enabled reliable traversability predictions even on previously untraversed and hazardous terrain. The proposed multi-source transfer learning framework achieved

a reduction in the slip prediction error by approximately 35% compared to single-source models trained on limited target data. Additionally, the method improved energy consumption estimation accuracy by 28%, demonstrating its effectiveness in generalizing to unfamiliar terrain with minimal prior observations. While AnyNav [47] is powerful, it relies heavily on labeled data, making Inotsume's method an important advancement for scenarios where data collection is dangerous or expensive.

Enhancing perception beyond onboard sensors by integrating aerial imagery from an assistive UAV, Fortin et al. [49] proposed a self-supervised framework for terrain awareness in off-road environments to address the limitations of ground-based vision systems. Traditional self-supervised approaches rely on proprioceptive feedback (e.g., vibrations, energy usage) and low-angle ground-level camera views, which often suffer from occlusions and reduced resolution at longer distances. In contrast, Fortin's framework combines terrain-aligned aerial imagery with ground vehicle data to train a ResNet18-based deep learning model and a lightweight MLP classifier for predicting terrain properties such as vibration intensity, bumpiness, and energy consumption. Using a forest dataset covering 2.8 km and comprising over 13,000 ground and aerial images,

the method achieved a 21.37% overall improvement in terrain property prediction accuracy, with gains reaching 37.35% in densely vegetated areas, where ground vision typically struggles.

While Fortin et al. [49] addressed sensory limitations using external agents, Vecchio et al. [50] confronted the labeling bottleneck by eliminating dependence on annotated datasets. They proposed a novel framework for terrain traversability estimation in robot navigation tasks, aimed at overcoming the dependence on large manually annotated datasets. The study formulated traversability estimation as a vector regression task applied to vertical bands of RGB video frames. To avoid manual labeling, the authors introduced a method that integrated self-supervision, synthetic dataset generation, and unsupervised domain adaptation (UDA). In the experimental setup, a model was first pre-trained using self-supervised learning to minimize the distribution gap between synthetic and real-world data, enabling the network to learn transferable features. This was followed by supervised training on synthetic videos, while an unsupervised domain adaptation loss function was employed to align feature representations between domains, enhancing generalization to real-world environments.

Lastly, Sathyamoorthy et al. [51] proposed TerraPN, a novel framework for unstructured terrain navigation in autonomous robots. TerraPN employs online self-supervised learning to infer terrain properties directly from robot-terrain interactions. The system utilizes RGB images of terrain surfaces and the robot's velocities as inputs, while the labels are derived from IMU vibrations and odometry errors experienced during navigation. This approach enables the robot to learn surface characteristics such as traction, bumpiness, and deformability without the need for extensive labeled data. A key innovation of TerraPN is its method for constructing a surface cost map that differentiates between smooth, high-traction surfaces (low navigation costs) and bumpy, slippery, or deformable surfaces (high navigation costs). This cost map is computed by non-uniformly sampling patches from the input RGB images, detecting boundaries between surfaces, which results in 47.27% lower inference times compared to uniform sampling and existing segmentation methods. TerraPN performs better than earlier studies in a number of navigational metrics. Success rates increased by up to 35.84% in different situations. Vibration cost reduced by up to 21.52%, suggesting more seamless navigation. The robot slows down appropriately on bumpy or deformable surfaces, with speeds up to 46.76% slower compared to previous methods. This work reinforces the trend toward online, adaptive learning, sharing the label-free advantage of Vecchio et al. [50], but applying it directly in a continuous navigation context.

D. Vegetation classification

Vegetation classification plays a critical role in smart forestry, as it directly impacts terrain traversability and obstacle perception. *In this review, the focus is less on botanical variety and species-level identification, but more on the dimension and spatial size of vegetation, since autonomous vehicles primarily require information relevant to navigation*

and obstacle avoidance. For example, distinguishing between low grass, dense underbrush, or tree trunks provides sufficient cues for identifying navigable versus non-navigable regions [52], without the need for fine-grained species classification. Moreover, vegetation characteristics strongly influence terrain properties such as slipperiness, softness, and the potential concealment of obstacles, all of which are essential considerations for motion planning, terrain adaptation, and operational safety. Reviewing vegetation classification methods thus provides a foundational basis for integrating semantic scene understanding into vision-based perception systems for forestry applications.

Recent advances in robotics and deep learning have triggered the development of autonomous systems for forest monitoring. A prominent trend across these studies is the integration of visual sensing and machine learning to enable real-time decision-making and environmental understanding. One of the earliest examples of this integration is the work by Fasiolo et al. [53] developed a mobile robotic system capable of autonomously navigating forest environments while estimating key tree characteristics, specifically the location and diameter of individual trunks. The system integrated two core technologies: SLAM and deep learning-based image processing, which were used to segment tree trunks and detect keypoints for trunk diameter estimation. Field trials were conducted using a skid-steered ground robot in a forest near Udine, Italy, where GNSS signals were weak or unavailable. The robot was equipped with LiDAR and cameras to collect 3D and visual data, which were fused for both navigation and tree trait estimation. Results demonstrated that the robot could navigate autonomously and avoid obstacles in GNSS-denied environments. The SLAM system, enhanced with loop closure, generated accurate forest point cloud maps with minimal positional drift. Additionally, the deep learning model, PercepTreeV1, achieved high-confidence tree trunk detection at a 98% threshold, highlighting the system's potential for automated forest inventory applications. Building on similar goals but shifting focus toward fire prevention and vegetation type classification, Mendes et al. [54] and Paulo et al. [55] investigated the use of object detection models (YOLOv5 and YOLOR) on RGB images captured by UGVs. Both studies tackled the challenge of distinguishing between hazardous and non-hazardous vegetation. While YOLOR showed higher mAP in some configurations, YOLOv5 consistently offered faster inference speeds, smaller model size, and better real-time performance critical factors for deployment in fire-prone forests. Interestingly, Paulo et al. extended the classification scope to include cut and dead vegetation, which directly informs risk mitigation strategies.

While RGB-based detection proved efficient, Silva [56] expanded the sensing modality to include thermal imagery, aiming for robust tree trunk detection under varying visibility conditions. A comprehensive set of experiments was conducted to evaluate the performance of deep learning-based object detection models for ground-level detection of forest tree trunks using both visible and thermal imagery. The authors created and publicly released a forestry dataset comprising 2,895 annotated images. Five object detection models were

selected and trained using this dataset: SSD MobileNetV2, SSD Inception-v2, SSD ResNet50, SSDLite MobileDet, and YOLOv4 Tiny. With an AP of 90% and an F1 score of 89%, YOLOv4 Tiny outperformed the other models in terms of detection performance, demonstrating its higher accuracy in recognizing tree trunks throughout the dataset. To evaluate appropriateness for real-time applications, inference speed was evaluated in addition to accuracy criteria. When implemented on a GPU, YOLOv4 Tiny achieved the fastest inference time of 8 milliseconds, once again outperforming the others in terms of efficiency. Navigation and control in natural environments require not just perception, but precise motion planning. Dengbin et al. [57] addressed this by introducing a novel visual-based trajectory tracking method for wheeled agricultural robots operating in rice paddy fields. The system combines a crop row detection algorithm based on region growth sequential clustering and Random Sample Consensus (RANSAC) with a model-based predictive controller to compute real-time steering commands. This dual-layered approach offers both robust trajectory generation from visual input and adaptive control based on the robot's dynamics, including slip modeling, which is often neglected in simpler kinematic control schemes. Empirical validation demonstrates that the algorithm achieves trajectory detection success rates exceeding 96.25%, with steering angle errors consistently below 3° , highlighting both its robustness and precision. The image processing time of 13.98 ms per frame further affirms the system's suitability for real-time field operations. Vegetation classification plays a vital role in forest ecosystem monitoring and ecological research, particularly when applied to hyperspectral image analysis. Traditional classification models often fall short in capturing the intricate spatial features and deep-level spectral-spatial interactions inherent in vegetation data. To address this limitation, Lei et al. [58] proposed a Deep Composite Kernel Extreme Learning Machine based on spatial feature extraction (DCKELM-SPATIAL) for hyperspectral vegetation classification. The approach incorporated advanced spatial feature extraction techniques by employing Gabor filters and super-pixel density peak clustering to construct a novel set of spatial composite kernels. This spatially enhanced kernel framework enabled the model to better capture localized texture and structure patterns, leading to improved discrimination among vegetation types. Experimental evaluations conducted on two real-world hyperspectral vegetation datasets reveal that DCKELM-SPATIAL significantly outperforms classical and state-of-the-art classification algorithms in terms of overall accuracy. Beyond 2D imagery, research has also advanced into 3D point cloud analysis for tree segmentation. Jonathan et al. [59] introduced TreeLearn, a deep learning-based pipeline designed for tree instance segmentation from laser-scanned forest point clouds, addressing the limitations of traditional hand-crafted segmentation algorithms in dense forest environments with overlapping canopies. Unlike classical methods that rely on rule-based identification of trunks and crown growth, TreeLearn adopts a data-driven approach, leveraging a fully automated workflow that requires minimal hyperparameter tuning, thus offering ease of deployment. The model was trained on a large-scale dataset of 6,665 tree

instances labeled using Lidar360, and further evaluated on a newly introduced manually annotated benchmark dataset containing 156 fully segmented trees, as well as the Wytham Woods dataset. Empirical results demonstrated that TreeLearn matched or exceeded the performance of the Lidar360 labeling algorithm and outperformed state-of-the-art methods such as SegmentAnyTree [60], ForAINet [4], and TLS2Trees [61]. Key contributions include: (1) the design of an end-to-end tree instance segmentation framework (TreeLearn); (2) the release of a high-quality, hand-labeled benchmark dataset for segmentation evaluation; and (3) comprehensive benchmarking against leading segmentation techniques, underscoring the generalizability and accuracy of the proposed method. Together, these studies illustrate a diverse yet converging set of approaches where robotics, deep learning, and advanced sensing modalities are collaboratively advancing the field of autonomous forest monitoring. While early work focused on proving feasibility in individual tasks like trunk detection or vegetation classification, recent research increasingly emphasizes multi-functional systems, real-time performance, and generalizability across environments. However, challenges remain in integrating perception with robust control under dynamic conditions and in building standardized datasets for cross-comparative evaluation.

III. OBSTACLE DETECTION

Obstacle detection represents a critical component of vision-based perception systems in forestry environments, enabling autonomous vehicles to identify and avoid hazards that could impede navigation or cause operational failures. Unlike structured environments, forests present a diverse array of obstacles that vary significantly in their nature, appearance, and detection challenges. This section provides a comprehensive review of obstacle detection methods, organized by obstacle types to provide clear insights into the specialized approaches required for different categories of hazards. The classification encompasses several key obstacle categories: terrain-related obstacles such as steep slopes and unstable surfaces; vegetation-based obstacles, including tree trunks, fallen logs, and dense undergrowth; dynamic wildlife that poses both collision risks and ethical considerations; environmental obstacles such as fire and smoke that create perception challenges; and ground-level debris, including rocks, stumps, and fallen branches. Each category presents unique detection challenges, from the camouflaged nature of wildlife to the dynamic behavior of environmental hazards, requiring perception strategies and specialized algorithmic approaches. This section allows readers to understand both the commonalities and distinctions between different obstacle detection methodologies, facilitating the selection of appropriate techniques for specific forestry applications and operational requirements.

A. Terrain-related Obstacles

In forest environments, the terrain itself often presents significant obstacles to autonomous navigation. Unlike structured urban roads, forest terrains are inherently irregular and dynamic, characterized by steep slopes, loose soil, wet or

TABLE I: Overview of reviewed studies in terrain classification.

Category	Past Studies	Contributions
Learning-based Approaches	Sandum et al. [9]	A U-Net based deep learning algorithm integrates multispectral imagery and ALS-derived canopy height models to segment forest stands, achieving 73% accuracy.
	Bello et al. [10]	A self-supervised convolutional autoencoder with an inpainting task pretrains a U-Net for high-resolution forest/non-forest mapping, improving performance under limited labeled data conditions.
	Meng et al. [11]	TerrainNet combines semantic and geometric terrain understanding through a multi-headed deep network for real-time off-road navigation.
	Wang et al. [13]	A lightweight CNN named <i>TSCSPNet</i> for terrain classification on resource-constrained field robots.
	Gao et al. [15]	A contrastive learning framework enhances fine-grained terrain segmentation, achieving 89.8% accuracy on benchmark datasets.
	Wang et al. [16]	A hybrid model combines CNN and support vector machine under limited computational resources.
	Guan et al. [17]	GANav uses group-wise attention to improve navigability-aware terrain classification.
	Hu et al. [18]	A CNN integrated with Conditional Random Field using PolSAR data.
	Pawel et al. [19]	A DNN trained on RGB-D data enables accurate terrain recognition, achieving 98.99% classification accuracy.
	Al Jarrah [20]	A two-stage approach integrates vanishing point estimation with fuzzy segmentation for terrain detection, reaching 96.43% accuracy.
	Fusic et al. [21]	A comparative analysis between U-Net and Mask R-CNN shows Mask R-CNN achieves superior terrain segmentation performance with 93% accuracy.
	Kumar et al. [22]	Transfer learning (ResNet50, VGG16, and InceptionV3) uses pre-trained models to enhance generalization.
	Shelare et al. [23]	StrideNET combines convolutional and transformer architectures to infer terrain properties from visual inputs for improved scene understanding.
	Chen et al. [24]	A vision transformer architecture fuses RGB-D inputs, achieving 97.64% accuracy on legged robots.
Fusion of Visual and Proprioceptive Features	Chen et al. [25]	A decision-level late fusion framework combines CNN trained on visual and proprioceptive inputs, achieving 96.4% classification accuracy across varied lighting conditions.
	Hsiao et al. [26]	A multi-modal terrain classification system uses fuzzy logic to fuse NIR and RGB inputs, enabling robust recognition in low-light environments with 99.7% accuracy.
	Sun et al. [27]	A legged robot framework fuses vision, IMU, force sensors, and IR data for semantic terrain segmentation.
	Wisth [28]	A factor graph-based system tightly integrates vision, IMU, LiDAR, and leg kinematics for robust and drift-resilient odometry in challenging terrains.
	Zürn et al. [42]	A cross-modal self-supervised learning method uses audio signals to supervise visual terrain classification, reducing dependency on annotated datasets.
	Ren et al. [29]	TOP-Nav integrates terrain appearance with wheel speed and IMU signals in unstructured environments.
	Wang et al. [30]	A weighted kNN classifier fuses visual and vibration signals, achieving up to 97% accuracy.
	Guan et al. [31]	VINet integrates visual and IMU in a unified network, achieving 98.37% accuracy.
	Zhao et al. [38]	Super Odometry tightly fuses vision, LiDAR, and IMU in an IMU-centric framework for robust navigation in degraded perceptual conditions.
	Elnoor et al. [39]	AMCO dynamically adjusts fusion weights among visual, wheel speed, and IMU signals in real time for reliable outdoor operations.
	Frey et al. [32]	A self-supervised ViT-based system for real-time terrain traversability learning and adaptation from raw visual sensory inputs.
	Cui et al. [33]	A support vector regression model learns a continuous mapping from visual features to traversability scores for terrain evaluation.
	Kurup et al. [34]	A fused feature set from camera and IMU inputs for an SVM-based terrain classifier, achieving 90% accuracy.
	Wang et al. [40]	A rescue robot framework fuses vision, LiDAR, and IMU to construct 3D elevation maps for terrain assessment.
Huang et al. [41]	The MOTC dataset enables visual and IMU-based terrain classification for extraterrestrial planetary surfaces.	
Skultety [36]	A comparative study evaluates CNNs and RANSAC-based methods for terrain characterization in forests.	
Terrain Property Estimation	Dong et al. [43]	A semantic segmentation model predicts terrain stiffness and friction properties directly from image inputs to support locomotion planning.
	Garen et al. [44]	An active terrain probing system uses force sensors to estimate surface collapsibility.
	Wang et al. [45]	A TV-Hybrid A* algorithm integrates terrain-aware and vehicle dynamics for friction-sensitive path planning.
	Parker et al. [46]	A Bayesian framework performs semantic elevation mapping to represent terrain properties probabilistically.
	Fu et al. [47]	AnyNav combines NNs and symbolic reasoning to estimate terrain friction for physics-aware navigation.
	Inotsume et al. [48]	A multi-source transfer learning approach with GPR estimates terrain traversability in data-scarce regions.
	Fortin et al. [49]	A self-supervised framework combines UAV and ground-level imagery for terrain property prediction.
	Vecchio et al. [50]	A self-supervised learning model with unsupervised domain adaptation estimates terrain traversability without requiring manual labels.
Guan et al. [51]	TerraPN learns terrain properties online using fused IMU and RGB data in a self-supervised manner to adapt to changing conditions.	
Vegetation Classification	Fasiolo et al. [53]	An integrated SLAM and deep learning approach for tree trunk detection and diameter estimation in GNSS-denied forest environment.
	Mendes et al. [54]	A comparative study evaluates YOLOv5 and YOLOR for detecting vegetation relevant to wildfire prevention.
	Silva [56]	A YOLOv4-Tiny trained using 2,895 images, achieving 90% average precision in vegetation detection.
	Fu et al. [57]	A vision-based crop row detection system combined with predictive control, enabling successful navigation in rice paddy fields with 96.25% success rate.
	Lei et al. [58]	A DCKELM-SPATIAL model uses composite kernels for hyperspectral vegetation classification with spatial regularization.
	Jonathan et al. [59]	TreeLearn uses DNN to segment individual trees from LiDAR point clouds.
	Paulo et al. [55]	A YOLOv5-based classification system identifies vegetation for fuel reduction tasks.

muddy patches, rocky surfaces, and other natural irregularities. These elements not only challenge the traversability of ground vehicles but also directly influence the risk of mechanical failure, slippage, or loss of control.

From a perception standpoint, terrain-related obstacles must be distinguished from traversable surfaces through semantic segmentation and terrain classification techniques. While these obstacles are not discrete objects (e.g., rocks or logs), they represent continuous spatial hazards that must be mapped and evaluated in real-time for safe path planning.

This paper has extensively discussed terrain classification methods in Section II. In the context of obstacle detection, terrain perception systems such as TerrainNet [11], TSCSPNet [12], and StrideNet [23] served a dual purpose: enabling surface-type recognition and identifying terrain regions that functionally behave as obstacles due to poor traction, instability, or steepness. Rather than duplicating the discussion, this section refers readers to Section II for a detailed review of learning-based and sensor-fusion approaches that classify terrain features and assess their navigability. These methods form the perceptual foundation upon which terrain-related obstacle avoidance is built.

B. Vegetation-based Obstacles

Vegetation in forest environments poses a variety of obstacles to autonomous systems, not only in the form of dense undergrowth but also as structural elements such as tree trunks, low-hanging branches, or fallen trees that can impede navigation or damage equipment. Unlike dynamic obstacles, these vegetation-based challenges are static yet irregular, often camouflaged by their surroundings. Detection of such obstacles requires robust semantic understanding of the scene. As reviewed in Section II-D, several methods, including PercepTreeV1 [53] and TreeLearn [59], employed deep learning and sensor fusion to identify tree trunks and foliage boundaries. While these methods were originally developed for inventory or mapping purposes, their semantic outputs (e.g., bounding boxes or instance segmentation) are highly applicable to obstacle detection pipelines. Additionally, systems like VERN [62] improved navigability through dense vegetation using few-shot learning, indirectly supporting obstacle avoidance by identifying traversable corridors. Integrating such vegetation-aware perception models into navigation systems enhances both safety and path planning in highly cluttered forest environments.

C. Wild Animals

The detection and monitoring of wildlife in complex forest environments present significant challenges due to factors such as limited visibility, occlusion, camouflage, and the unpredictable behavior of animals. Traditional detection methods, often reliant on manual observations or basic sensor technologies, are limited in scope and scalability. Consequently, recent advancements in deep learning have provided powerful tools for object detection tasks, and models such as the YOLO series have been widely adopted for real-time applications.

Standard YOLO models, such as YOLOv5m and YOLOv5s, struggle in complex environments where wildlife is elusive and blends into the background [63], especially when lightweight models are required for edge devices. To address this, Ma et al. [64] proposed WL-YOLO, a lightweight model for detecting 14 wildlife species (e.g., Amur Leopard, Amur Tiger, Badger, Black Bear, Leopard Cat, Musk Deer, Red Fox, Red Panda, Otter, Sika Deer, Weasel, Wild Boar, Wolf and Marten) in dense forest environments. WL-YOLO integrated a MobileNetV3 backbone, reducing parameters by 44.73% compared to YOLOv5m, enabling faster inference while maintaining high detection quality. It achieved an mAP of 97.25%, F1-score of 95.65%, and accuracy of 95.14%, while shortening detection time by 58%. Additionally, the model incorporated the Convolutional Block Attention Module (CBAM), combining spatial and channel attention to better detect small or partially obscured animals, enhancing robustness in cluttered natural scenes.

Recent efforts in real-time animal detection for forest environments reflect a growing emphasis on integrating lightweight deep learning models with IoT frameworks to reduce wildlife-vehicle collisions and human-animal conflicts. For instance, Girish et al. [65] proposed an IoT-based real-time animal detection and vehicle alert system to prevent accidents on forest highways. The system integrated sensors, a Raspberry Pi, and a Pi Camera for live monitoring, using the YOLO algorithm to detect animals with high-speed object recognition (processing up to 45 frames per second). Upon detection, visual alerts (e.g., warning lights) were triggered at a safe distance, particularly effective during nighttime. The core contribution lay in combining YOLO-based image detection with real-time IoT alert mechanisms to enhance driver awareness and reduce human-animal collision incidents. This work was notable for merging high-speed object detection with IoT-driven real-time alerting mechanisms, offering a practical solution for forest environments. Building upon the use of edge devices, Bandari et al. [66] developed a system that uses deep learning and computer vision to detect and classify wild animals in forest border areas. The model ran on a Raspberry Pi, processed live video, and distinguished wild animals from humans and domestic animals. When a wild animal was detected, the system sent an alert using LoRa communication, which was better suited for remote areas where WiFi or GSM might not work. Different from [65], this work broadened the detection scope beyond animals and strengthened communication reliability in off-grid regions.

While both of these systems emphasized detection and alerting, Viji et al. [67] took a step further by incorporating tracking capabilities through DeepSORT, paired with a YOLOv4-based detector trained on a custom dataset of nine animal classes. Achieving an mAP of 98%, their system focused on continuous monitoring, demonstrating how detection could be extended into dynamic tracking for better situational awareness. A complementary direction was explored by [68], which tackled the issue of animal-vehicle collisions (AVC) that pose a serious threat to both road safety and wildlife conservation, especially in forested areas where visibility is low and animal movement is unpredictable. It introduced an

Fig. 4: WL-YOLO model for wild-life detection [64].

animal detection and collision avoidance system that used object detection techniques, specifically SSD and Faster R-CNN. A key contribution was the creation of a new dataset covering 25 animal classes with over 31,000 images. Using this dataset, the authors trained and evaluated detection models, achieving solid performance: 80.5% mAP at 100 fps with SSD, and 82.11% mAP at 10 fps with Faster R-CNN. The work stood out for combining a wildlife dataset with high-performing detection models to support real-time AVC prevention in forested or rural road settings. Unlike the edge-focused models described above, this dataset-driven approach prioritized high detection accuracy through conventional deep learning methods, though at the cost of greater computational demands. Expanding the detection scope into aerial monitoring, Aditya et al. [69] presented DEAL-YOLO, a modified object detection framework aimed at improving small animal detection in UAV imagery, which was especially useful for wildlife conservation in complex forest environments. The model introduced several key innovations: it used multi-objective loss functions (WIoU and NWD) to improve localization precision, incorporated Linear Deformable convolutions for efficient feature extraction, and added a Scaled Sequence Feature Fusion module to enhance multiscale feature representation. Notably, DEAL-YOLO adopted a two-stage inference strategy to refine detection in low-confidence regions, which was particularly effective for small and hard-to-spot animals. Compared to baseline models like YOLOv8-N, DEAL-YOLO achieved similar or better performance with

significantly fewer parameters (up to 69.5% less), making it both accurate and lightweight for aerial wildlife monitoring. Compared to ground-based systems, this UAV-based solution prioritized lightweight inference from elevated perspectives, suitable for conservation monitoring in complex terrains.

Recent advancements in object detection have increasingly focused on optimizing models for deployment in resource-constrained environments, particularly in remote forested regions where real-time wildlife monitoring is critical. A notable contribution in this domain is a streamlined variant of YOLOv5s, called WildARe-YOLO [70], specifically engineered for wild animal recognition under limited computational capacity. The authors proposed architectural modifications to the backbone by integrating Mobile Bottleneck Block modules alongside an enhanced StemBlock, effectively reducing the model's computational burden. To maintain detection accuracy despite these reductions, they introduced Focal-EIoU as a bounding box loss function and adopted a BiFPN-based neck structure for improved multi-scale feature fusion. Empirical results demonstrated substantial performance gains, including a 17.65% increase in frame-per-second (FPS), a 28.55% reduction in model parameters, and more than a 50% decrease in floating-point operations (FLOPs) compared to the baseline YOLOv5s. These improvements significantly enhanced the model's suitability for deployment in forest environments, particularly on low-power edge devices such as mobile units or solar-powered sensors, without compromising recognition performance.

To further push the envelope in real-world detection scenarios, Chappidi et al. [71] introduced an animal detection approach based on YOLOv7, aimed at improving accuracy and speed in complex outdoor environments, specifically optimized for challenging forest environments. The authors benchmark YOLOv7 against several established models, including YOLOv3-spp, YOLOv5s, and Faster R-CNN and found that YOLOv7 consistently outperformed them across key metrics. The model achieved a high mean Average Precision (mAP) of 96.03%, along with strong precision, recall, and F1 scores, and an average detection time of just 0.025 seconds per image. These results show that YOLOv7 is not only accurate but also fast and resilient in real-world field conditions, making it well-suited for practical wildlife monitoring tasks.

UAVs have emerged as a pivotal tool for wildlife detection due to their mobility, coverage, and ability to capture both RGB and thermal imagery in various environmental conditions. Recent developments have seen the integration of machine learning and deep learning (ML-DL) models into wildlife detection workflows. These approaches have demonstrated considerable accuracy, especially when applied to high-resolution UAV imagery. The combination of RGB and thermal data has proven particularly effective in enhancing object visibility and detection performance in cluttered or low-light environments. However, most ML-DL approaches require extensive labeled training data and computational resources, making them less viable for real-time applications in the field. To address these limitations, Seunghyeon et al. [72] introduced a training-free detection method based on the Sobel edge detection algorithm, offering a lightweight alternative to deep learning approaches. The proposed method generates six types of edge-enhanced input images (RGB only, Thermal only, Fur color Temp corrected, Unnatural color removal, RGB + Thermal and RGB + Corrected Thermal) based on contextual factors and applies edge detection without the need for pre-trained models. This results in high-speed detection, with the fastest time per image recorded at 0.033 seconds, suitable for processing all frames of thermal videos in near real-time. While this approach offers considerable advantages in processing speed and simplicity, its performance metrics, a maximum detection precision of 0.804 and a recall of 0.699, remain below those achieved by more advanced DL-based systems. Moreover, the low resolution of thermal sensors and height limitations of UAV-based data collection reduce their effectiveness in broader applications. Nonetheless, the method showcases a promising alternative for scenarios where real-time performance and low computational requirements are prioritized over detection accuracy. Beyond real-time monitoring, camera-trap-based approaches offer insights into long-term biodiversity tracking. For example, Kutugata et al. [73] demonstrated that relatively simple deep learning models can be effectively trained for camera-trap image classification with region-specific wildlife. Using a dataset of 120,000 images provided by California Institute of Technology (Caltech), the authors trained a binary classifier for detecting nilgai (*Boselaphus tragocamelus*) with 97% accuracy and a multiclass model that distinguished 20 animal groups plus a "none" category with 89% accuracy. The DL model consists of only 6 convo-

lutional layers. A key contribution is the evaluation of model transferability: when the multiclass model was applied to camera-trap data from a different region (southwestern United States), its performance dropped sharply in both precision and recall. This result underscores that camera-trap classifiers trained on one region's species distribution may not generalize well elsewhere, highlighting the importance of region-specific training data and careful consideration of model scope in conservation applications.

In a similar vein, Alekss et al. [74] introduced a new camera-trap dataset combining different open-source datasets (e.g. Caltech Camera Traps, North America Camera Trap Images, WCS Camera Traps, Island Conservation Camera Traps, etc.) of wild ungulates collected in Latvia over four years and established baseline performance for automated detection and classification. The authors tested RetinaNet and Faster R-CNN with ResNet50 backbones, training both for ten epochs and evaluating with mAP across multiple IoU thresholds. Faster R-CNN achieved the best mAP@0.5:0.95 of 0.2786 (early in training) but showed unstable performance across epochs, while RetinaNet reached a comparable peak of 0.2659 with more stable dynamics. Additional experiments showed that pretraining significantly improved RetinaNet's learning efficiency, whereas oversampling sometimes reduced per-class accuracy, especially for deer. Both models achieved more than 25% average precision for boar and deer detection, but performance dropped when animals were small, distant, or partially occluded. Compared with YOLOv4 and SSD, their three-module approach with RetinaNet and Faster R-CNN backbones outperformed those baselines at key IoU thresholds.

D. Environmental Obstacles (Perception Challenges)

In forest environments, fire represents not only a natural hazard but also a dynamic and unpredictable obstacle that poses significant risks to both autonomous systems and surrounding ecosystems [75]. From a perception and navigation perspective, the ability to detect active fires or fire-prone conditions is critical for safe route planning, real-time obstacle avoidance, and operational decision-making [76]. Incorporating a review of fire risk assessment and fire detection methods expands the scope of vision-based perception in forestry, underscoring the importance of integrating environmental awareness into autonomous systems for improved resilience and safety.

Ground-based fire detection emphasizes the integration of computer vision, ground mobility, and sensor-based IoT systems to address the challenges of real-time monitoring under varied environmental conditions. In this direction, Kong et al. [77] introduced a ground-based firefighting mobile robot (FFMR), integrating a real-time fire detection system. The FFMR was a crawler-based mobile platform equipped with a rotatable camera, an early warning system (sound and light alerts), and a micro fire extinguisher. The authors proposed an enhanced version of YOLOv3-Tiny that incorporated a Spatial Pyramid Pooling (SPP) module and refined the multi-scale anchor mechanism. These changes allowed the model to better detect small fire targets under outdoor occlusion. Compared to

YOLOv3-Tiny, the new model achieved a mAP of 90.10%, while reducing model size by 21.04%. It also operated at 34.55 FPS, offering a good trade-off between detection accuracy and speed. The model outperformed YOLOv2-Tiny, YOLOv3-Tiny, and YOLOv4-Tiny in terms of accuracy while maintaining real-time performance. While Kong et al. [77] focused on robot-based detection and response, Avishek et al. [78] presented a dual-approach forest fire monitoring system that combined IoT-based environmental sensing with machine learning-based fire prediction. The system integrated a low-cost Arduino platform with sensors for temperature (DHT11), humidity, and flame detection, along with a GSM module for sending real-time alerts. The IoT setup was capable of triggering an alarm when smoke or flames were detected in the surrounding environment, providing immediate local warnings. On the predictive side, the authors utilized a particular machine learning model using 15 geographic and environmental features, including temperature, humidity, and oxygen levels. It identified three key predictive features from the 15 inputs, which were used in a user-facing web tool for live forest fire risk prediction. Users could input climate parameters and receive a real-time percentage likelihood of fire occurrence. Together, the IoT-based sensing system and the SVM-based predictive model provided both immediate fire detection and proactive risk forecasting, offering a practical tool for forest management. The modular design, low hardware cost, and web interface made it scalable and potentially deployable across a range of forest environments. In a more computationally efficient direction, Vipin [79] proposed a rule-based color classification algorithm for forest fire detection using image processing. The method used both RGB and YCbCr color spaces to classify fire pixels. The use of YCbCr was particularly effective for separating luminance from chrominance, helping to distinguish actual flames from similar-colored objects. The algorithm defined seven explicit rules based on pixel values in the two color spaces to identify fire regions. It was tested on two datasets, one containing fire, the other with fire-like visuals. The model achieved a flame detection rate of 99% and a false alarm rate of 14%. Because the algorithm involved only simple arithmetic operations that scaled linearly with image size, it was computationally efficient and suitable for real-time deployment in forest fire monitoring systems. Moreover, Sucuoglu et al. [80] introduced a fire detection system that operated effectively under both day and night conditions by combining RGB and near-infrared (NIR) vision. The core innovation lay in its four-stage hybrid-cascade machine learning model, which fused outputs from multiple specialized models for robust detection: YOLOv10 for fast object localization, Mask R-CNN for fine-grained fire segmentation, ConvLSTM-FireNet to capture flame flickering over time, and DenseNet for improved classification under varied lighting. These models were trained separately on RGB and NIR image datasets and then combined to use their complementary strengths. This fusion allowed the system to handle environmental variability, including low-light conditions. The system achieved F1 scores of 96.7% (daytime) and 95.9% (nighttime) on labelled fire/non-fire datasets, with an IoU of 82.4%. Deployed on a Raspberry Pi-powered robot, it maintained real-time perfor-

mance at about 18 FPS and could reliably detect fire sources from a safe approach distance of 500 mm. Despite its strong accuracy, this model's real-time performance was limited by the high computational cost of Mask R-CNN. The authors suggested exploring lighter segmentation networks and model compression in future work.

Aerial vision-based fire detection faces significant challenges from environmental factors such as smoke, terrain variation, changing illumination, and visual clutter. To address these perception difficulties, researchers have increasingly combined deep learning, multi-modal imaging, and explainable AI (XAI) to enhance robustness in complex conditions. The field has undergone a fundamental transformation in methodological approaches over the past decade. Early computer vision-based methods predominantly relied on hand-crafted features and rule-based systems, establishing foundational principles that would later inform more sophisticated approaches. Yuan et al. [81] exemplified this traditional paradigm by developing a color-motion fusion approach that utilized the CIE Lab color space to segment high-chromaticity fire-like regions while employing optical flow to detect irregular flame motion patterns. This dual-feature approach successfully addressed the critical challenge of distinguishing actual flames from static red objects, establishing motion analysis as a key discriminative factor that remains relevant in contemporary systems. Building upon these color-motion fusion principles, subsequent research expanded into multi-modal sensing approaches that leveraged complementary imaging modalities. Xie et al. [82] advanced this concept through a sophisticated dual-light UAV system that strategically combined multiple color spaces and imaging techniques. Their approach integrated YCrCb color space for flame detection with HSV for smoke detection, while incorporating infrared grayscale imaging to construct comprehensive flame and smoke masks. This multi-modal integration not only improved overall accuracy but significantly enhanced early smoke detection capabilities, addressing one of the most challenging aspects of wildfire monitoring where smoke often precedes visible flames. Balachandran et al. [83] proposed an Enhanced Learning with Fire Classification Model (ELFCM), which integrated learning algorithms with categorization rules specifically designed for smoke and fire detection. Their validation against Random Forest Classifier baselines demonstrated the effectiveness of combining domain-specific knowledge with machine learning techniques, establishing a framework that would influence subsequent hybrid approaches.

The adoption of deep convolutional architectures marked a paradigm shift that delivered substantial performance gains across the field. This transformation was clearly demonstrated through comparative studies that highlighted the superior capability of deep learning models. Utkarsh et al. [84] provided compelling evidence of this advancement by comparing CNN and R-CNN models for aerial wildfire imagery, with R-CNN achieving 97% accuracy compared to CNN's 92% after identical 20-epoch training regimens. This performance differential illustrated not only the power of region-based detection but also established accuracy benchmarks that became standard references for subsequent research. Akanksha et al. [85] in-

roduced an innovative pipeline that merged edge detection and thresholding preprocessing with CNN feature extraction, subsequently enhanced by YOLOv4 implementation within the Darknet framework [86]. This hybrid approach enabled fast and multi-scale detection capabilities while maintaining the interpretability advantages of traditional preprocessing methods, demonstrating that the integration of classical and modern techniques could yield superior results than either approach alone. Moreover, transfer learning emerged as a particularly powerful strategy for achieving exceptional performance with limited domain-specific training data. Comprehensive architectural comparisons revealed significant performance variations among different pre-trained models. Shouthiri et al. [87] conducted systematic evaluations of five pre-trained CNNs (VGG16, ResNet50, MobileNetV2, Xception, Inception) against a custom model, identifying Xception as the top performer. This finding was further validated by Davis et al. [88], who demonstrated that transfer learning with Xception as a backbone could achieve a remarkable 99.21% accuracy on the DeepFire dataset, establishing new performance standards for the field.

The development of specialized detection frameworks has addressed specific operational requirements while maintaining high performance standards. YOLO-based methods have been particularly optimized for real-time wildfire detection scenarios. Zhang et al. [89] utilized YOLOv8's capabilities to detect small and partially obscured fires in live surveillance feeds, specifically targeting early-stage ignition alerts where rapid response is most critical. This work addressed the challenging scenario where fires were small and potentially hidden by vegetation or terrain features, representing conditions most relevant to practical fire prevention systems. Furthermore, the pursuit of both high accuracy and interpretability has led to sophisticated ensemble approaches that combine multiple architectural strengths. Tanvir et al. [90] created an ensemble combining ResNet50V2 and InceptionV3 that achieved 98% accuracy while incorporating LIME and Grad-CAM for interpretability. This approach demonstrated that high performance need not come at the expense of explainability, addressing critical requirements for deployment in safety-critical applications where decision transparency is essential. Meanwhile, real-time deployment considerations have driven the development of optimized inference systems. Li et al. [91] addressed these practical constraints by deploying YOLOv7 on an RK3588 edge server with a PyQt5 interface, achieving reduced inference latency suitable for real-time monitoring applications. This work bridged the gap between research-level performance and practical deployment requirements, demonstrating the feasibility of deploying sophisticated detection systems in field conditions. Moreover, the demand for autonomous surveillance systems has necessitated the development of lightweight models suitable for deployment on constrained devices. Arunkumar et al. [92] conducted comprehensive assessments of deep learning models on the FLAME dataset, evaluating MobileNetV2 [93], EfficientNetB0 [94], NASNetMobile [95], and ResNetV2101 [96] for their suitability in resource-limited environments. Their findings revealed that MobileNetV2 achieved 98.1% accuracy while

maintaining computational efficiency suitable for embedded systems, leading to successful integration into an ESP32-based UAV system for autonomous fire surveillance. This work established the feasibility of deploying high-performance detection systems on autonomous platforms without requiring constant connectivity to powerful computing resources.

The integration of explainable AI techniques has emerged as a critical development for improving trust and adoption in automated fire detection systems. Qiao et al. [97] applied Grad-CAM to YOLO-based wildfire detection, generating class-discriminative heatmaps that highlighted the most influential regions in aerial imagery. This visualization approach enables operators to understand and validate system decisions, particularly important in emergency response scenarios where false positives or negatives can have significant consequences. The ensemble method developed by Tanvir et al. [90] further advanced this concept by pairing LIME with Grad-CAM to provide comprehensive explanations of high-confidence predictions while maintaining their 98% accuracy performance, demonstrating that interpretability enhancements do not necessarily compromise detection performance.

The incorporation of environmental context into fire modeling represents an important advancement in understanding fire behavior and risk assessment. Wu et al. [98] employed Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) with CNN and Faster R-CNN architectures to extract terrain features predictive of fire spread in mountainous areas. This approach demonstrated the value of integrating topographic data for comprehensive risk assessment and ecological forecasting, extending fire detection systems beyond simple presence/absence classification toward predictive modeling of fire behavior and spread patterns. Specialized detection tasks have revealed the varying complexities of different fire-related phenomena. Ehab et al. [99] developed a UAV-based texture-color method specifically targeting the detection of thin and dense smoke from dry leaf ignition sources. Their achievement of a microaverage F1-score of 0.865 across test videos and 0.870 on real UAV footage highlighted the increased difficulty of smoke detection compared to flame classification, reflecting the inherent challenges in early-stage wildfire perception under complex environmental conditions.

Collectively, these studies illustrate a clear evolutionary trajectory from DEM-driven environmental modeling and handcrafted feature fusion to high-accuracy deep learning models, explainable frameworks, and resource-efficient deployments. The performance progression is remarkable: while early traditional approaches achieved modest accuracy levels, most contemporary image-based fire classifiers report accuracy exceeding 95%, with several surpassing 98% and some, like Xception-based transfer learning approaches, reaching over 99%. However, smoke detection systems typically achieve F1-scores around 0.86 to 0.87, consistently underscoring the continued challenges in early-stage wildfire perception under complex environmental conditions. This performance differential between flame and smoke detection represents a key area for future research focus, particularly given that early smoke detection is often more valuable for fire prevention than flame detection after fires have fully developed.

Fig. 5: An enhanced version of traditional YOLOv5 model called YOLO-LFD for advanced detection of wild-fire [100].

E. Debris and Ground-Level Obstacles

Accurate detection and localization of debris and low-level obstacles such as stones, stumps, or uneven terrain is critical for safe navigation of autonomous systems in forested environments. Recent works have approached this challenge from multiple technical directions, ranging from stereo vision and voxel-based mapping to lightweight CNNs for real-time applications. An automatic object detection and localization system was implemented in [101] using a stereo camera configuration combined with the YOLO object detection algorithm to identify and localize ground obstacles, specifically stumps and large stones on harvested forest land. The system computed object positions in 3D space based on stereo vision data and was evaluated by comparing automatically derived positions against manually labeled ground truth data. Testing was conducted across a designated area, assessing both detection reliability and positional accuracy. With a detection success rate of 98% and a mean positional error of 0.33 meters over distances of 1 to 10 meters, this approach demonstrated the effectiveness of combining deep learning with stereo vision for localized obstacle monitoring. While Li et al. [101] relied on conventional stereo matching followed by object detection, another study [102] proposed StereoVoxelNet to address the gap between high-performance stereo-based obstacle detection and the stringent compute constraints of onboard robotic systems. Instead of relying on traditional stereo matching to obtain dense disparity maps, they designed a lightweight deep neural network that directly predicts 3D occupancy voxels from stereo image pairs. This model encoded volumetric obstacle distribution without explicit point cloud reconstruction, thereby significantly reducing both memory and computational requirements. To further optimize efficiency, StereoVoxelNet

incorporated a coarse-to-fine pruning strategy using octree-based spatial partitioning during decoding. The decoder dynamically constructed octree structures, enabling the network to concentrate its inference on safety-critical regions while pruning irrelevant free space. Results showed that the approach achieved real-time performance on the NVIDIA Jetson TX2 platform, accurately detecting obstacles up to 32 m away. Remarkably, it achieved superior Intersection-over-Union (IoU) and Chamfer Distance (CD) scores compared to state-of-the-art stereo methods, while consuming only approximately 2% of their computational cost. Complementing these stereo vision approaches, Yang et al. [103] proposed an obstacle detection and avoidance method for mobile inspection robots operating in complex terrain, with a focus on transmission line inspection. The core technical contribution was an improved CNN model designed for real-time obstacle recognition using visual input. The model was specifically optimized to capture obstacle distribution and shape in terrain environments, which was critical for reliable navigation. For obstacle avoidance and path planning, the method integrated a potential field approach that adjusted the robot's trajectory based on the detected obstacle locations and their distance to the target area. This allowed the robot to autonomously plan and follow a safe and efficient path. Unlike [101] and [102], which concentrated on detection and localization, this work emphasized end-to-end autonomy, integrating perception with navigation in unstructured environments. In terms of results, the proposed CNN-based recognition system outperformed baseline methods, including the artificial fish swarm algorithm (AFSA), SVM, and PSO, in both accuracy and processing efficiency. The experimental evaluation, conducted in a simulated inspection environment, demonstrated that this approach reduced obstacle recognition error and supported fast and reliable autonomous navigation.

IV. CHALLENGES AND CONCERNS

In the forestry domain, vision-based perception systems face a unique set of challenges, with two of the most critical being the lack of large-scale and high-quality datasets, as well as the lack of robust and domain-specific simulation platforms. Publicly available labelled datasets for forestry tasks (e.g., tree and stump detection, species classification, terrain recognition, and obstacle identification) are extremely limited, and most available vision datasets originate from agricultural or urban environments. This scarcity can be traced to the limitations of current LiDAR data sources, which primarily come from terrestrial laser scanning (TLS) and aerial laser scanning (ALS). TLS provides the highest point cloud density, yet its application is restricted by the limited mobility of equipment, intensive labor requirements, and poor time efficiency, making it impractical for large-scale deployment. By contrast, ALS offers flexibility and cost-efficiency, reducing fieldwork demands and enabling coverage of broad areas. However, the distance from the ground hinders its ability to capture fine-scale ground features that are critical for perception tasks. Moreover, much of the existing forestry research treats trees as the primary subject of interest, while understory vegetation,

TABLE II: Overview of reviewed studies in obstacle detection.

Category	Study	Contributions
Wild Animals	Zhibin et al. [64]	A lightweight YOLO variant integrating MobileNetV3 and CBAM for real-time detection of 14 forest animal species, and is optimized for edge deployment, achieving 97.25% mAP.
	Girish et al. [65]	A YOLO-based IoT system built on Raspberry Pi to identify animals near highways and trigger vehicle alerts through warning lights to reduce collision risks.
	Bandari et al. [66]	A deep learning system using Raspberry Pi and LoRa communication for real-time monitoring of wild animals near forest borders to reduce human-animal conflict.
	Viji et al. [67]	A forest animal tracking framework combining YOLOv4 and DeepSORT for continuous multi-class detection and tracking, achieving 98% mAP.
	Saxena et al. [68]	A SSD and a Faster R-CNN models for real-time animal detection, evaluated using a self-constructed dataset of 31,000 images across 25 animal classes. The mAP and detection speed of both methods are 80.5% at 100 fps and 82.11% at 10 fps for SSD and faster R-CNN, respectively.
	Aditya et al. [69]	A UAV-based model using deformable convolutions and scaled feature fusion for small animal detection, reducing parameters by 69.5% compared to YOLOv8-N.
Environmental Obstacles (Perception Challenges)	Kong et al. [77]	A real-time fire detection system based on an improved YOLOv3-Tiny model.
	Avishek et al. [78]	An IoT and learning-based system for early forest fire detection using sensor fusion and remote monitoring.
	Vipin et al. [79]	A rule-based classifier using both RGB and YCbCr colour spaces for fire pixel detection in forest.
	Hilmi et al. [80]	A four-stage hybrid cascade classifier using RGB and NIR inputs, achieving 96.7% F1-score for fire detection.
	Wu et al. [98]	Combined Digital Elevation Models with CNN and Faster R-CNN architectures for improved fire detection in forested terrain.
	Balachandran et al. [83]	A classical machine learning technique, Random Forest Classifier, for forest fire detection.
	Wang et al. [104]	A lightweight YOLO variant optimized with data and feature enhancement techniques for real-time forest fire detection on embedded platforms.
	Fan et al. [105]	A streamlined version of YOLOv4 designed for fast and accurate forest fire detection with reduced computational cost, namely YOLOv4-Light.
	Wang et al. [106]	Replace YOLOv4's backbone with MobileNetV3 to reduce parameters by 62.78% and achieve 0.666 mAP in forest fire detection.
	Bai et al. [107]	A transfer learning with VGG-16 for forest fire classification, enabling rapid training and generalization on small datasets.
Ground-Level Obstacles	Li et al. [101]	Used a stereo camera and YOLO for real-time detection and localization of ground-level forest obstacles such as stumps and large rocks.
	Li et al. [102]	A lightweight 3D deep network that predicts occupancy voxels from stereo image pairs for obstacle-aware navigation, namely StereoVoxelNet.
	Yang et al. [103]	An improved CNN to enhance detection accuracy and robustness for forest ground-level obstacles.

terrain variation, and ground conditions—elements central to autonomous navigation are often regarded as noise. Issues of scale, accuracy, and research focus thus jointly constrain the availability of datasets that are sufficient for training vision-based forestry systems. Such datasets fail to reflect the inherent complexity of forestry scenes, where dense vegetation, irregular lighting, seasonal variation, and frequent occlusions significantly affect image quality and feature visibility. Data scarcity is further compounded by the diversity of forestry environments worldwide. For example, boreal, temperate, and tropical forests differ drastically in colour palettes, canopy density, and ground texture, requiring extensive and region-specific visual data for robust generalization. Rare but operationally critical events, such as animal crossings, unexpected tree falls, or equipment failures, are especially underrepresented, limiting model preparedness for edge cases. Annotation remains a major bottleneck, as dense foliage and overlapping objects increase labelling difficulty, while tasks such as species identification or tree health assessment demand expert-level forestry knowledge, further driving up cost and time requirements. Proprietary restrictions from forestry companies and government agencies often limit the open sharing of imagery, LiDAR scans, and operational footage, slowing collective progress in dataset expansion.

Equally significant is the lack of advanced simulation

platforms capable of representing the complexity of real forestry operations. Popular simulators like CARLA, AirSim, and Gazebo are designed primarily for urban or structured environments, with simplified vegetation models and flat terrain profiles. They lack realistic rendering of natural light variation, seasonal foliage changes, vegetation motion due to wind, and dynamic occlusion from falling branches or moving wildlife. Domain-specific forestry simulators, where they exist, often prioritize machine operation or harvesting productivity rather than high-fidelity visual realism, leading to a substantial simulation-to-reality gap when deploying vision models trained solely in simulated conditions. The absence of standardized forestry-specific benchmark environments prevents fair and consistent performance evaluation across research efforts, further slowing methodological advancement.

Integration challenges compound the issue: incorporating forestry-specific machinery models, such as harvesters, forwarders, and autonomous logging trucks, into simulators often requires extensive custom modelling and sensor calibration. Realistic interaction physics between terrain, vegetation, and machinery, such as branch bending, ground deformation under heavy loads, or soil texture changes after rainfall, are rarely implemented with the detail necessary for testing perception algorithms. Multi-modal sensor simulation, including synchronized RGB, thermal, hyperspectral, and LiDAR data informa-

tion, is often unsupported or poorly aligned with forestry operational needs. Without such capabilities, it becomes difficult to develop and validate perception algorithms for real-world challenges, such as detecting small obstacles in undergrowth, differentiating between tree species under varying seasonal conditions, or identifying safe navigation paths through partially obstructed trails.

These constraints create a significant barrier to progress in forestry robotics and automation. The limitation of diverse, representative, and well-annotated datasets limits model robustness and generalization, while the absence of high-fidelity, benchmarked simulation platforms hinders scalable experimentation and safe pre-deployment testing. Addressing these gaps, through collaborative dataset creation, open-source forestry-specific simulators, and improved domain adaptation techniques, will be essential for advancing vision-based perception capabilities in autonomous forestry operations.

V. FUTURE TRENDS

This review paper has primarily focused on vision-based perception approaches for autonomous navigation in forestry. However, relying solely on camera systems presents several inherent limitations, including sensitivity to lighting conditions, difficulty in accurately estimating distances to objects, and challenges in distinguishing between solid obstacles and passable terrains. These limitations can significantly impact navigation performance in complex outdoor environments where reliable depth perception and material properties assessment are crucial.

Future developments in off-road navigation will likely emphasize multi-modal sensor fusion, particularly integrating LiDAR systems with visual perception to address the above challenges. The combination of RGB imagery with LiDAR data can provide complementary information: cameras excel at texture analysis and semantic understanding, while LiDAR offers precise geometric measurements and vegetation density assessment. This fusion enables more robust classification of traversable versus non-traversable terrain elements, especially in vegetated environments [62] where visual appearance alone may be misleading.

Beyond LiDAR integration, emerging sensor technologies such as Ultrasonic sensors [108]–[111], radar systems [112], [113], thermal imaging [114], and tactile sensors [115]–[118] present additional opportunities for enhancing perception capabilities. Radar can provide reliable detection through adverse weather conditions, while thermal sensors can reveal material properties and vegetation characteristics that are invisible to standard cameras [119]. The integration of these diverse sensing modalities, combined with advanced machine learning techniques, promises to deliver more comprehensive and reliable perception systems.

Furthermore, the development of adaptive perception systems that can dynamically adjust their sensing strategies based on environmental conditions and mission requirements represents another promising direction. Such systems could optimize sensor usage, computational resources, and navigation strategies in real-time, leading to more efficient and robust autonomous navigation capabilities.

STATEMENT ON THE USE OF GENERATIVE AI TOOLS

This manuscript was proofread using ChatGPT-5, an AI-powered language model developed by OpenAI. The tool was used to refine grammar, enhance clarity, and improve the readability of the text. All technical content, data interpretations, and conclusions were independently reviewed and verified by the authors to ensure accuracy and integrity. The use of ChatGPT-5 was solely for linguistic and stylistic improvements, with no influence on the scientific or analytical aspects of the manuscript.

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